

INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN GERMAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING: FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING AS AN INTERCULTURAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the problem of formation of intercultural communicative skills in the process of learning foreign languages. Efficient intercultural communication implies awareness of the native culture and other cultures, the ability to analyze behavior, lexical and grammatical norms of different cultures. The techniques described in the article allow revealing the creative potential for learning the country of the language that is studied, mentality of people, art, history, culture.

Keywords: intercultural communication, foreign language, intercultural dialogue, intercultural communication barriers.

INTRODUCTION

Intercultural competence is becoming increasingly important due to ongoing migration and globalization. Especially in business, intercultural skills are missing, which can and always is a hindrance to successful cooperation. But knowledge of and understanding of cultural differences is not only of great importance within economic processes. In schools and authorities, it is now assumed that employees have an understanding of *foreign* cultures, *foreign* thoughts and actions [1].

Our contribution is therefore divided into two parts: In a first step, we show how intercultural communication in the classroom can be conceptualized and made analytically tangible. In a second step, we describe a specific university didactic approach, namely casuistry in teacher training, and show a practical example.

Communication is a basic need of human life. As Paul Watzlawick wrote in his book “Human Communication”, it is impossible not to communicate [2].

“When people come into contact with one another, worlds collide.”

Language presents culture; Communication takes place through language. Learning a foreign language means coming into contact with a foreign world, recognizing other rules and traditions and understanding other values and mentalities.

The principle of interpersonal communication is characterized by a sender wanting to communicate something to a receiver. This message must in turn be deciphered by the recipient - i.e. understood as the sender intended it. If the message sent is not interpreted correctly, no communication has taken place. However, if the message is decrypted correctly, there is communication and the receiver in turn informs the sender of information that must now be correctly understood by the sender.

The teacher should use a contrastive approach in foreign language teaching, i.e. draw attention to the similarities and differences between the two cultures. Intercultural competence in foreign language teaching enables students to accept differences but also to recognize fundamental similarities between people [3].

The intercultural approach developed from the second half of the 1980s. It represents a further development of the pragmatic-functional concept, the audio-visual and the communicative methods. Didactics and methodology place more emphasis on the target groups and their cultural and linguistic origins. The intercultural approach should be integrated into language teaching, either consciously and organized or unconsciously, but always subliminally. It requires the use of media such as images, videos, audio samples, art, music, etc. [4].

Intercultural competence and the resulting ability for intercultural communication are intended to prepare people for a longer stay abroad, i.e. for foreign cultural communication situations, with the help of role plays, presented intercultural misunderstandings, films and social background information. The learners should be able to recognize foreign cultural ways of thinking, behaving and speaking and relate them to their own. Ultimately, they are able to react adequately to strangers and act adequately themselves.

Intercultural learning arises in a situational learning process between people from different cultures and is based on interactions between them. There are three reasons for intercultural learning. Against the background of a multicultural society, you can deal with racism, reduce prejudices and achieve a development towards tolerance. In order to establish and maintain international business contacts, intercultural learning was used in the training of managers. As far as pure language contact is concerned, this type of learning is aimed at the cultural nature of one's own linguistic actions and, against the background of foreign language teaching, at the peculiarities of everyday life, the habits and ways of thinking of the foreign society. Die aff ektive Komponente von IL beeinfl usst Haltungen gegenüber dem Fremden und

We use the definition of *the content of intercultural learning* according to GEHRING (2002, 69), since intercultural learning is clearly aimed at IC and is tailored to the needs of teaching in schools. Intercultural learning (IL) consists of three components:

- The *affective component* of IL influences attitudes towards the strange and unfamiliar.
- The *cognitive component* of IL is based on knowledge about factual and value-related aspects of foreign cultural perceptions.

The interactional component of IL is realized as the ability to establish and maintain contact [...] within a social framework that is accepted for speakers and listeners, whereby mutual acceptance and recognition are reflected in appropriate sociolinguistic signals (GEHRING: 2002, 69, emphasis I.H.).

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Intraculturality can be described as the different understanding of the same culture that results from different education, social status and/or professional affiliation [5].

In didactics, we largely understand intercultural competence to be the ability to perceive foreign cultural circumstances from multiple perspectives, to have empathy and critical tolerance towards the foreign culture and its people, and thus the ability to understand the foreign culture, the role expectations of its members and their actions, to have strategies to deal with phenomena of one's own and foreign culture and thus to interpret the foreign world against the background of one's own - and vice versa [6].

One method is the representation of intercultural communication situations between Germans and foreigners, whereby typically intercultural communication topics and rituals are made the subject of reflection. Another possibility is to present meaning as a culture-shaped unit, whereby learners are made aware of external perspectives and diversity of perspectives. Another possibility is to present intercultural communicative misunderstandings. In this way, misunderstandings that arise in conversation due to culture-related ideas are discussed; stereotypical ideas, associations, different scopes of terms and relationships between expressions and speaking intentions are also discussed [7].

One of the methodological means in foreign language teaching is games. Playful activities enable dynamic learning and help students master the content more easily. Playing is one of the innovative learning models and involves linking educational content and promoting motivation and thus the effectiveness of learning. Different types of games can positively influence the development of intercultural competence in foreign language teaching [6].

Play is one of a child's most important activities that develops numerous skills, abilities and attitudes. It is an important factor in the development and maturation of the child and a means by which students absorb reality and develop in cognitive, motor-sensory, psychomotor and socio-affective senses [7]. For a seven-year-old child, playing is a way of learning. The teacher must turn most activities in foreign

language lessons into a kind of game in which the child will participate with movements and speech expression. The ideal activities for students of this age are activities that have the appearance of play and fun and are quick and lively with lots of movement [1].

CONCLUSION

Intercultural competence has already established itself as an important component of foreign language teaching, mostly in the form of intercultural regional studies, which, however, only deals with the culture of the target language. Since all languages are linked to the culture of the respective language community, teaching German as a foreign language is also very suitable for teaching IK. This article suggested that Daf lessons be used more in the future to impart such IK, which is not only limited to the cultures of German-speaking countries. The proposal is based on the observation that the German language is gradually losing its importance as a world language and that a new goal of the German language as a foreign language is necessary.

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